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On the User Experience of Moodle as a Tool for e-Learning in Theoretical Computer Science

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INTRODUCTION

In introductory courses on theoretical computer science the failure rates and the level of frustration amongst the students are often very high (e.g. [1], [2]). This article reports on a study in such a course where supplementary e-learning units were used to improve motivation and the acquisition of competencies. Instead of designing a new platform, we decided to base our project on existing tools that are easily accessible for this approach. The open source learning management system (LMS) Moodle² was chosen to provide students with the learning units. These units consist of learning content, interactive exercises and bonus pages. The learning content was available both as videos and texts. The bonus pages could be unlocked by achieving sufficiently high scores in the exercises. To provide alternative ways through the so-called lessons

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² <https://moodle.org/>

containing the learning content, learning paths were used to support individual learning in our heterogeneous group of students more effectively.

In such an approach, the user experience (UX) of the used platform plays an important role as it can complicate or simplify the usage for the students. The developers of Moodle state themselves that usability as part of the UX is an important part of the platform [3] and several studies were conducted to establish a better understanding of the usability and the whole UX of learning management platforms. In [4] Machado and Tao compared the UX for Moodle and the well-known LMS Blackboard. The overall results suggest that Moodle has the better UX for the user. Graf and List [5] examined several platforms and found that Moodle outperforms the other platforms concerning adaptivity and usability. In contrast, Kirner, Custodio and Kirner [6] conducted a study with usability experts resulting in all other platforms used in this study outperforming Moodle concerning usability. The usability and the whole UX of a platform with such a wide range of possible uses is hard to grasp. Therefore, in our study we focus on a specific and important use case and try to determine its UX. The main contribution of this paper is the presentation of an approach for learning units which is applicable in many disciplines and affordable as it is based on an open source platform and ensuring the UX quality of this approach.

In this article, we first discuss the requirements for the used system, then the design of the learning units and underline in which points our usage deviated from the standard Moodle installation. After a short overview of the study's structure, we further present our findings concerning the UX of our learning units and give an outlook on further possible research issues.

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1 REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGN

1.1 General requirements

Our approach was to use a system that was easily accessible, familiar to our students and that supported the use of learning paths and interactive exercises. Moodle is well-known and popular with almost 100.000 registered installations [7] and used in our university as the mandatory platform for course management. Therefore, the students are already familiar with using this platform in general, although for another purpose. As it is open source, no additional costs were involved.

The learning units were created using design recommendations based on the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) by Sweller [8] and several theories based on the CLT.

1.2 System design

We conducted two separate studies with similar design in two different courses. Our intention for this was to demonstrate the flexibility of the approach. The first course was an introductory course for theoretical computer science about formal languages and automata (FLAT), the other one was a more advanced course on modelling

concurrency, bisimulation equivalence and fixed point theory. Due to the study's structure, two learning units were created for each course, covering the learning content of two course weeks each. A learning unit consisted of several blocks similar to the one presented in *Figure 1*, covering one subtopic each. A block consists of a headline, a short overview of this subtopic, one or more lessons (marked by three blue linked boxes) containing the actual content and several multiple-choice-exercises, additional exercises (marked by the red checkmark) and a bonus page (here it is still greyed out), which could be unlocked if at least 75 percent of the exercises were answered correctly. Any exercise could be done repeatedly to improve the results.

Schwache Bisimulation

Mit starker Bisimulation haben wir eine gute Möglichkeit kennengelernt, Prozesse zu vergleichen. Aber geht es vielleicht noch besser? Abhängig vom Blickwinkel, der gerade nötig ist, schon.

In diesem Teil der Lerneinheit wollen wir uns anschauen, wie wir von Handshakes als Teil des sichtbaren Verhaltens abstrahieren können, also wann es okay für uns ist, wenn tau-Aktionen unsichtbar sind. Dafür sehen wir uns die Definition und die Eigenschaften von schwacher Simulation und darauffolgend schwacher Bisimulation an und wie wir damit Beweise führen können.

- **Schwache Bisimulation**
- **Aufgaben zu schwacher Bisimulation und Bisimulationsbeweisen**
- **Bonus - schwache Bisimulation**

Eingeschränkt Nicht verfügbar, es sei denn:

- Sie haben die erforderliche Punktzahl in Schwache Bisimulation erhalten
- Sie haben die erforderliche Punktzahl in Aufgaben zu schwacher Bisimulation und Bisimulationsbeweisen erhalten

Fig. 1. One learning unit consists of several blocks similar to this one.

Figure 2 presents a cutout of a typical content page of a lesson with a headline, buttons to view this content as a video or to view the graph of the lesson structure and below the actual content. *Figure 3* presents another cutout of the end of the same page where the buttons below offer the possibility for users to decide whether they want introductory exercises for the next content part (left) or rather want to go straight to the explanation (right).

(A) Einführung

ALS
VIDEO
ANSEHEN

GRAPH
ANSEHEN

Mit der starken Bisimulation haben wir ja jetzt da
damit auch gut Beweise führen. Was wollen wir n
außen. Bei starker Bisimulation können wir aber i
Prozess $\tau.0$, bei dem nur eine Handshake-Aktion

Es kann für die Betrachtung aber durchaus einen
stellen wir uns mal zwei Geheimagenten vor, die r

Dabei kann man sich leicht Szenarien vorstellen, bei denen
sondern auch solche, bei denen es schon Probleme gibt, w

Idealerweise sollte eine solche Art Prozesse zu vergleichen
alle Eigenschaften gelten.

Machen wir uns also auf den Weg und sehen uns als näch

Erstmal eine Übung (B)

Gleich zur Erklärung (C)

Fig. 2. Part of a lesson content page with options for video content or the lesson graph

Fig. 3. Part of a lesson content page with options to do an introductory exercise first or to jump straight to the next explanation

SEITENMENÜ

- (A) Einführung**
- (B) Übung zu schwacher Simulation**
- (C) Erklärung schwache Simulation**
- (D) Aufgaben zu schwacher Simulation**

p_1

$\downarrow a$

p_2

$\downarrow b$

p_3

q_1

$\downarrow \tau$

q_2

$\downarrow a$

q_3

$\downarrow b$
 $\downarrow b$

q_4 q_4

Gilt $p_1 \sim q_1$?

Ja

Nein

Fig. 4. A part of a navigation menu in a lesson

Fig. 5. Exercise in a lesson.

Within a lesson the user can always see a navigation menu, as in *Figure 4*, to simplify jumping directly to another part of the lesson, if desired. *Figure 5* presents an exercise, a simple multiple-choice-question. When answered, the system presents the users with a feedback text to give a better understanding why their selected answer was correct or incorrect. Especially the latter design - with an appropriate level of detail and an encouraging wording - takes considerable effort in preparation.

1.3 Changes in Moodle

Only minor alterations in Moodle were made for the learning units. This allows for similar units to be created for another course as easily as possible. In the lessons a button (as in *Figure 2*) was added for each content page to view the textual content as a video and to navigate from the video page back to the textual content. This was necessary due to our requirement to make content available as both text and video. Embedding the video in the textual page would have led to a longer loading time of the webpage. As, during the test phase, some students were occasionally confused about the different available paths in a lesson we added another button that opened a simple graph showing the structure of the lesson. Several modules of Moodle were *not* used in our learning units (competencies, other types of exercises, ...); this was mainly due to the idea to keep the learning with these units simple and not to overload the units, neither for educators nor for students.

2 EVALUATION

2.1 Methodology

As the first rollout with the advanced course only had a very small number of participants we focus in this article mainly on the results of the introductory course. The study was conducted in a repeated measures design where, after an initial survey, the students were divided into two groups A and B to balance out gender differences, previous knowledge and motivation. For the first two weeks, group A was allowed to use the first learning unit; then, after another survey measuring motivation and competencies for both groups and UX of the platform for group A, group B was allowed to use the second learning unit for two more weeks. This was followed by another survey similar to the one before. So the students had the possibility to use the platform for two weeks before they filled out the corresponding questions. More information about the questionnaires and more details of the study can be found in [9]. For the current article we concentrate on the measurement of UX.

The UX was measured using the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) [10] and additional open questions which were analysed through qualitative content analysis [11]. The UEQ measures the UX on six scales: Attractiveness, Perspicuity, Efficiency, Dependability, Stimulation and Novelty. It consists of 26 item pairs (e.g. annoying/enjoyable) that each mark the extremes on a seven-point likert scale. Due to a technical error one of these item-pairs (belonging to the scale novelty) was not used in the surveys.

Additionally, students could participate in short interviews after the study was finished where they were asked, inter alia, for advantages and disadvantages of the platform. These interviews were analysed through qualitative content analysis as well.

2.2 Results

One set of answers of the UEQ was not evaluated due to a high number of inconsistencies in the answers. After this cleanup, there was a total number of N=45 of filled out UEQs. Our findings are summarised in *Table 1* and presented in a more graphical way in *Figure 6*. The official UEQ-Handbook [12] states that a value less than -0,8 is seen as a negative evaluation. A value between -0,8 and 0,8 represents a neutral evaluation and a value larger than 0,8 represents a positive evaluation. The scales for our learning units therefore all have a positive evaluation except for Novelty, which is evaluated as neutral. Possible explanations are the missing item-pair which might have changed the mean or because the students already were acquainted with Moodle in general beforehand, so for them it was not a new platform in general.

Table 1. Results of the UEQ

Scale	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Confidence	Confidence interval ($p=0,05$)	
Attractiveness	1,441	0,961	45	0,281	1,160	1,721
Perspicuity	1,131	0,986	45	0,288	0,843	1,420
Efficiency	1,028	0,928	45	0,271	0,757	1,299
Dependability	1,035	0,795	45	0,232	0,803	1,268
Stimulation	1,265	0,819	45	0,239	1,026	1,504
Novelty	0,689	1,001	45	0,292	0,396	0,981

Fig. 6. Graphic representation of the results (figure created with official UEQ-Tool [12])

Figure 7 presents our results compared to a benchmark based on data from 9905 persons from 246 studies on different products [12] made available by the developers of the UEQ. Here our learning platform is above average for the scales Attractiveness, Perspicuity, Efficiency and Stimulation and below average for Dependability and

Novelty. Dependability measures if the user feels in control of the interaction [12]. As the value for Dependability is still good in general we will not interpret this further.

Fig. 7. Result compared to a benchmark (figure created with official UEQ-Tool [12])

The open questions in the survey were filled out by 29 participants in total. Their answers to the two questions on problems handling the learning units and possibilities for improvements differ strongly, but more than half of the participants mentioned problems with the navigation when asked for the handling of the platform. In further development, this should be considered.

In the additional interviews students were mainly asked on their motivation to participate in the study and the pros and cons of the platform; the UX was not a specific target of the questions. Overall the feedback of the 8 participants (5 from the introductory course, 3 from the advanced course) was positive with all of them stating that the learning units were useful when trying to understand the course content. Negative feedback came less frequently and differed more. One student, for example did not like the navigation of the platform, another one did not like that the content of the videos was identical to the textual explanations. We did not get negative feedback on specific points by a majority. As navigation was no major point in the interviews, we assume the negative feedback to be due to individual preferences.

3 SUMMARY

The study reported in this article gave an insight on the UX of Moodle for the complementary use in a university course for a special use case. On the whole, the UX of this approach turned out to be well. Although, in the open questions several participants mentioned problems with the navigation this was not reflected by the questionnaire and therefore probably did not strongly influence the UX. A similar use case that should be investigated for Moodle (or other LMS) is how the addition of other modules influences the UX. H5P³, for example, allows for several other types of questions, especially questions inside of videos. Other use cases for LMS that could be interesting to look into are the UX in blended learning scenarios, MOOCS, flipped classroom scenarios or for exercises and assignments in more classical teaching situations. An advantage of the approach reported in this article is the transferability into other contexts and topics. As we used an open source platform and did not need

³ <https://h5p.org/>

any tools specific for theoretical computer science, this approach can easily be used for courses of other disciplines.

The studies are about to be repeated at several other universities to confirm the results and find out more about how motivation and the acquisition of competencies are influenced by supplementary use of learning units.

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